

Status of Women Empowerment in Rural Bihar through Rural Development Programme : A Sociological Study

*Sonam Rani**

Discrimination against women in all spheres of life has been a worldwide phenomenon; however, it appears more acute in developing nations like India. According to UN Human Development Report 2013, India has been ranked 136 among 187 countries evaluated for Human Development Index (HDI). Moreover in Gender Inequality Index India has been ranked 132 among the 148 countries for which data is available. In India, only 10.9 per cent of the parliamentary seats are held by women, and 26.6 per cent of adult women have reached a secondary or higher level of education, compared with 50.4 per cent of their male counterparts. India ranks badly on the Maternal Mortality Ratio as well. For every 100,000 live births, 200 women die of causes related to pregnancy. Female participation in the labor market is 29 per cent, compared with 80.7 percent for men.

Even after more than sixty years of the functioning of Indian democracy the struggle of women to get equal rights and opportunities continues throughout the country. However, the status of women in the states of southern states has shown signs of significant improvement, the other states, particularly the Hindi heartland states have lagged behind. As per the provisional census of India 2011, the total population of Bihar was 103.80 million. Of this, the rural population stands at 92.07 million and the urban population, 11.73 million. The growth rate of population during the last decade was 25.07 percent. Bihar has recorded the highest decadal growth rate in rural population in the country. The overall sex ratio of Bihar which was 919 in 2001 has fallen by 3 points to 916 in 2011. The total literacy rate of Bihar is 63.82 percent. In rural areas, the literacy rate is 61.83 percent and in urban areas, it is 78.75 percent.

The Male literacy rate of 73.39 percent (Rural-71.90, Urban-84.42) is much higher than the female literacy rate of 53.33 percent (Rural-50.82, Urban-72.38). The gender gap in literacy rates both in rural as well as urban areas has narrowed marginally for the State as a whole. Bihar that ranks third in population (8.58% of India population) among the major states of India has a very low ranking in terms of human development. In a comparison of 23 major states, the undivided Bihar ranked 21 in its Human Development Index (HDI) and 35 (out of 35) in Gender Development Index (GDI). These indices imply that Bihar, in terms of expansion and use of capabilities, for both men and women, depicts a dismal scenario. The consequence of being a low Human Development Index (HDI) state is far worse for women as reflected in the lowest GDI position of the state. Bihar is one such Hindi speaking state which has gained endemic nature of social and economic backwardness. According to a recent study conducted by the Rajiv Gandhi Foundation, 26 out of the 100 poorest districts in India are from Bihar. This constitutes more than two-third of the state. In a state where more than 40% of the population live below the poverty line and more than 80% of the population live in the pitiable conditions of rural areas to talk of the marginalization of women separately has been considered meaningless. It means that women suffer not only as a result of being from the families that have lower access to opportunities and capabilities but also on account of their gender which culturally deprives them of social and economic opportunities.

* NET (UGC), Research Scholar (Sociology) Patliputra University, Patna

Therefore, the point that we wish to emphasize is that the pervasive nature of Bihar's social and economic backwardness has prevented researchers in focusing on vital social sectors concerning women and as a result the overall condition of women in the state has remained neglected domain. As a consequence, a clear scrutiny of women in Bihar offers a peculiar situation that arises out of triple discrimination, first as being a women; second, being member of a backward region and third belongs to rural area. In addition, unfortunately, very few studies are available related to measurement of level of empowerment of women contributing factors for it.

The approach as used by development bodies and the offered quantitative indicators tend to reduce its scope to women's ability to take individual responsibility by their own. The indicators do not consider changes in economic and social structures, those that refer to collective empowerment, linked to social change. Various literature have shown that while it is important to look at the quantitative aspect, for example the number of women holding a management position in a firm or a political mandate, and this is not enough. The notion of empowerment goes further, questioning the roles of different players, men and women, within development policies; and getting people to think about: Conflicts and power, but also to examine symbolic referents and deep social structures. All of this opens up new doors to development. Therefore, this study also has been designed to focus that allow to measure empowerment both at individual and collective level.

Empowerment of women also means equal status to women. Empowering women socio-economically through increased awareness of their rights and duties as well as access to resources is a decisive step towards greater security for them. Empowerment includes higher literacy level and education for women, better health care for women and children, equal ownership of productive resources, increased participation in economic and commercial sectors, awareness of their rights and responsibilities, improved standards of living and acquiring self-reliance, self-esteem and self-confidence. Even after more than 63 years of Independence, positive spell of modernisation and industrialisation, development of Science and Technology, entering into space and nuclear age, the status of women in India continues to be low. Under the customary law, women have no right to inheritance of property either from father or husband. After her death or remarriage/marriage it goes to other family male members. It shows the lower status of women. These days cases of rape, dowry death and physical exploitation of women have gone up in rural areas. Women of all ages from four years to 70 years are reported being raped. Similar is the case of dowry deaths.

It is most unfortunate and tragic scenario of our society. So many Acts for safeguard of women have been enacted, i.e. Article 44 through 86th Amendment of Constitution of India as well as other enactment. Provisions of these Amendments say that women should be given special social security, to give more education with a view to provide more employment. Such and many more are cruel realities amidst which, she is struggling to breathe and wade through life's long and tedious journey. Undoubtedly the various developmental programmes initiated by the government and different organisations or the Non-Government Organisations (NGOs) have put their focus on women's over all development. Their basic approach is to inculcate confidence among women and bring about awareness of their own potential for development. This would certainly give them their due place as equal partners in all development programmes. Government may also make policy of reservation or incentives as they also constitute half of population and do not have proper representation in any material aspect of life.

Empowerment is multi-faceted, multi-dimensional and multi-layered concept. Women's empowerment is a process in which women gain greater share of control over resources—materials, human and intellectual like knowledge information, ideas and financial resources like access to money and control over decision-making in the home, community, society and nation, and to gain 'power'. According to a Report of the Government of India, "Empowerment means moving from a position of enforced powerlessness to one of power". Man and woman are both equal and both play a vital role in the creation and development of their families in particular and the society in general: Man and woman have got equal right and position in the Constitution of India, even then the question of empowerment of woman is one of the major issue in the process of development of countries all over the world. In India, Government had made Empowerment of Women as one of the Principal objectives of Ninth Five Year Plan (1997-2002) and also declared 2001 as the year of "Women's Empowerment". In order to give a fillip to empowerment of women and appropriate institutional mechanisms and interventions have been consciously built into the development design. The launching of Rashtriya Mahila Kosh, Indira Mahila Yojana, Mahila Samridhi Yojana, reserving of one-third of the number of seats in panchayats and the local bodies are programmes launched with a view to improve and empower women socially, economically and on political frontiers. Women have always and almost everywhere been on the fringe of political and social power. Like other states Bihar is no exception and continues to have marginal representation of its women in political institutions. Now that the Bihar Government has announced 50 per cent reservation for women PRI candidates and 15 per cent of the total budgetary allocations for 10 departments was earmarked for the empowerment of women in the state. Even then the gender ratio in Bihar was 921 women against thousand men. The population of women was 39.7 million as against 43.2 million of men. Women literacy rate is just more than half of men. For the empowerment of women Bihar Government has provided 720 million for Chief Minister Balika Poshak Yojana, Rs.421.4 million for Balika Cycle Scheme, Rs.200 million for Kanya Vivah Scheme, Rs.225 million for Nari Shakti Yojana. Besides this, the Government has earmarked Rs. 51.5 million for Swamsidha, Rs.539 million for Lakshmi Bai Social Security Scheme, Rs.138 million for National Programme for adolescent girls, Rs. one billion for supplementary nutrition, Rs.49 billion for Indira Awas Yojana and Rs.144.5 million for Dular strategy.

Study Area :-

This study concentrated in the rural areas of Vaishali district of Bihar. The Vaishali districts falls under the administrative jurisdiction of Tirhut Commissioner. Vaishali district is most important place of Bihar and also famous in India. It is the birth place of Lord Mahavir who was 23rd tirthankar of Jan Dharma. Vaishali on the north is surrounded by Muzaffarpur District, The river Ganga on south and Patna on the south of Ganga River, the National Highway (NH) 77 and railway line on the west and extends upto Reserve Police Station on eastern limit. Hajipur is the headquarter of Vaishali. It is also headquarter of Railway zonal office of Eastern Central Railway. Possibly due to the location the oldest and the first republic of the world flourished at Vaishali at a distance of 25 km from the district Muzaffarpur. The remains of the glorious Lichchvi's palace, Vijay Ashtambha or Ashoka's pillars, coronation pond attest the annihilation of the republic and the victory of Magadh Emperor. Amidst the alluvial fertile plain Vaishali evolved as a central place of trade and commerce and education since long. At present Vaishali is the medium service centre of North Bihar Plain serving the region with its educational, medical, cultural and commercial functions. It is linked with its region with a good network of rail and road transport. The

district Vaishali is only 20 kms north of the capital of Bihar which is also the largest city of Bihar. Kathmandu, the capital of Nepal and an international tourist centre is well connected with this city by road. The district is linked with broad gauge railway with Gauhati (910 km), Kolkata (587 km) in the east, Mumbai (1864 km) in the south west and Varanasi in the west is 280 km away from Vaishali.

Introduction of Respondents :

Table – 1
Introduction on the basis of Caste

Caste	Number	Percentage
Upper Caste	25	25
Backward Class	20	20
Other Backward Class	22	22
Scheduled Caste	27	27
Scheduled Tribe	06	06
Total	100	100

Table – 2
Introduction on the basis of Age

Age	Number	Percentage
18 - 28	10	10
28 - 38	16	16
38 - 48	22	22
48 - 58	28	28
58 - 68	16	16
Above 68	08	08
Total	100	100

Table – 3
Introduction on the basis of Education

Education	Number	Percentage
Post-Graduate	18	18
Graduate	27	27
Intermediate	17	17
Matric	22	22
Non-Matric	05	05
Technical & Others	11	11
Total	100	100

Findings of the Study and Analysis of the Data :-

Table – 4
Are You Know about Women Empowerment ? Yes/No

Respondent	Number	Percentage
Yes	58	58
No	42	42
Total	100	100

It is clear to above table that ask the question Are You Know about Women Empowerment then 58 percent respondent says that they know about Women Empowerment But 42 percent says that they not know about Women Empowerment.

Table – 5

Are You Know about Rural Women Empowerment Programme ? Yes/No

Respondent	Number	Percentage
Yes	70	70
No	30	30
Total	100	100

It is clear to above table that ask the question Are You Know Rural Women Empowerment Programme then 70 percent respondent says that they know about Women Empowerment But 30 percent says that they not know about Women Empowerment.

Table – 6

Do you know that Government, NGOs and various oher agencies promote gender equality ? Yes/No

Respondent	Number	Percentage
Yes	68	68
No	32	32
Total	100	100

It is clear to above table that ask the question Do you know that Government, NGOs and various oher agencies promote gender equality then 68 percent respondent supported that question But 32 percent has not supported that question.

Table – 7

Do you know that today women has empowerd ? Yes/No

Respondent	Number	Percentage
Yes	100	100
No	00	00
Total	100	100

It is clear to above table that ask the question Do you know that today women has empowerd then 100 percent respondent supported this question.

Empowerment is a self-generating and multi-dimensional process, where involving activity for advancement of women in different fields of life such as economic, political and social empowerment can be considered a change in the context of woman’s and man’s life that enables her/him increased capacity to lead a human life, characterised by external quality related to health, education, awareness, status and security. Empowerment means individual acquiring the power to think, act freely, exercise choice, voice and decide autonomy and fulfillment of their potentials. In other words, empowerment means to create free and fair circumstances where the individual has the rights to determine his/her own future lifestyle. The process of empowerment of women in Bihar has recently been paid attention by passing the Bihar Panchayati Raj Act, 1993, whereby 50 per cent of the total number seats reserved for SCs, STs and OBCs has been reserved for women in Panchayati Raj Institutions (PRIs).

Today we have noticed different Acts and Schemes of the central government as well as state government to empower the women of India. But in India women are discriminated and marginalized at every level of the society whether it is social participation,

political participation, economic participation, access to education, and also reproductive healthcare. Women are found to be economically very poor all over the India. A few women are engaged in services and other activities. So, they need economic power to stand on their own legson per with men. Other hand, it has been observed that women are found to be less literate than men. According to 2001 census, rate of literacy among men in India is found to be 76% whereas it is only 54% among women. Thus, increasing education am ong women is of very important in empowering them. It has also noticed that some of women are too weak to work. They consume less food but work more. Therefore, from the health point of view, women folk who are to be weaker are to be made stronger. Another problems is that workplace harassment of women. There are so many cases of rape, kidnapping of girl, dowry harassment, and so on. For these reasons, they require empowerment of all kinds in order to protect themselves and to secure their purity and dignity. To sum up, women empowerment can not be possible unless women come with and help to self-empower themselves. There is a need to formulate reducing feminized poverty, promoting education of women, and prevention and elimination of violence against women.

References :-

- Agarwal, B (1997): Bargaining and gender relations within and beyond the household. *Feminist Economics* 3(1): 1–51.
- Batliwala, Srilatha (1994): The Meaning of Women’s Empowerment: New Concepts from Action. Pp. 127-138 in *Population Policies Reconsidered: Health, Empowerment and Rights*.
- G. Bisnath, S, Elson D (2005): Women’s empowerment revisited. 256 S. Mosedale Copyright #2005 John Wiley & Sons, Ltd. *J. Int. Dev.*
- Census of India (2011): Provisional Tables, Registrar General of India.
- Duflo, Esther (2011): Women’s Empowerment and Economic development. NBER Working Paper No. 17702 (Revised January 2012) JEL No. D1,O1,012.
- Foucault M (1980): *The History of Sexuality: An Introduction*, Vol. 1. Penguin: Harlow.
- Govindasamy, Malhotra A and Pavavalalli (1996): Women’s Position and Family Planning in Egypt. *Studies in Family Planning* 27(6):328-340.
- Human Development in South Asia (2000): *The Gender Question*, The Mahbub ul Haq Human Development Centre, Oxford University Press, 2000.
- India Human Development Report 2011, IAMR and Planning Commission Indiressan, J (1999): Empowering women, challenge to educational institutions. National Conference on Empowerment of Women for Na tional Development, Dhole, pp. 15-19.
- Inglehart,R., and Welzel, C (2005): *Modernization, Cultural Change and Democracy: The Human Development Sequence*. Cambridge University Press.
- Jejeebhoy, Shireen J. and Zeba A. Sathar. (2001): Women’s Autonomy in India and Pakistan: The Influence of Religion and Region. *Population and Development Review* 27(4):687-712.
- Kabeer, N (2001): Reflections on the Measurement of women’s Empowerment.‘ In *Discussing Women’s Empowerment-Theory and Practice*’, Sida Studies No. 3.
- Lawson, S (2008): “Women Hold Up Half the Sky”, Goldman Sachs Global Economics Paper No. 164, page 2.4 March. The Goldman Sachs Group. Available at: <http://www@goldmansachs.com>
- Malhotra A et al. 2002. *Measuring Women’s Empowerment as a Variable in International Development*. Gender and Development Group, The World Bank: Washington, DC.
- Mason, Karen and Herbert L. Smith. (2000): Husbands’ versus Wives Fertility Goals and Use of Contraception: The Influence of Gender Context in Five Asian Countries.‘ *Demography* 37(3):299-311.

- Mosedale, S (2005): *Assessing Women's Empowerment: Towards A Conceptual Framework*. *J.Int. Dev.* 17, 243-257.
- Narayan, D (2002): *Empowerment and Poverty Reduction*, Washington, DC, World Bank.
- Nussbaum, Martha (2000): *'Women and Human Development: The Capabilities Approach'* New York: Cambridge Press.
- Oxaal, Zoe with Sally Baden. (1997): *Gender and Empowerment: Definitions, Approaches and Implications for Policy'*, Bridge Report No. 40. Sussex: Institute of Development Studies.
- Rowlands, Jo, Sen G and Germaine A (1997): *Population Policies Reconsidered: Health, Empowerment and Rights, Questioning Empowerment: Working with Women in Honduras*. Oxfam: Oxford.
- Sen, Amartya(1990): "More Than 100 Million Women Are Missing," *The New York Review of Books* 37 (20).
- Stotsky, JG (2006): *'Gender and its Relevance to Macroeconomic Policy: A Survey'*, International Monetary Fund Working Paper No. 06/233.10. International Monetary Fund: Washington, DC. Ph.D. Synopsis 14.
- Tzannatos, Zafiris (1999): *Women and Labor Market Changes in the Global Economy: Growth Helps, Inequalities Hurt and Public Policy Matters*. *'World Development* 27(3) : 551-569. University Press: Cambridge.
